

Digivet Stakeholder Workshops: Theoretical Framework

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Introduction

There is an urgent need to collate and characterise the relevant data being collected across the Nordic countries and the UK in order to identify shortcomings and opportunities for improving data accessibility and interoperability, and to contribute software tools and metadata libraries that will facilitate international collaboration, support disease prevention and preparedness, and underpin a wide range of future research in animal and human population health.

The DigiVet project aims to gather information about how digital data relating to the livestock sector and related animal health and welfare services is acquired, managed and used in the UK and Scandinavia to support decision making relevant to foodborne, animal and zoonotic diseases (such as *Salmonella* infections, African swine fever, antimicrobial resistance (AMR)). The longer-term goal of the DigiVet project is to work with stakeholders to produce a series of prototype decision-support tools for livestock data analysis and visualisation to improve the use and return value of digital data in the sector.

In this briefing, we present a framework which is intended to support workshop efforts to operationalize a “data to knowledge” continuum, and proactively shape the pathway from research to impact.

Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework adapted from Zhang et al. 2021 to understand the components of the data lifecycle which are “necessary to produce real world data usable for analysis”¹. We used this framework as a starting point by which we could identify, compare, and contrast enabling societal, technological, environmental, economic, and political (STEEP) drivers and barriers (as identified by stakeholders) to data digitalisation and innovation of new technologies in veterinary services.

¹ Zhang J, Symons J, Agapow P, Teo JT, Paxton CA, Abdi J, et al. (2022) Best practices in the real-world data life cycle. PLOS Digit Health 1(1): e0000003. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal>

Stakeholders' perceptions of current challenges, opportunities and knowledge gaps

This project involves the use of participatory workshops with key national stakeholders in UK, Sweden and Denmark, to explore the challenges in data digitalisation and identify key opportunities for developing solutions. The workshops were designed slightly differently due to differing requirements of the stakeholders in each country, but all were based on the same theoretical framework.

In the UK workshop we specifically considered:

- What currently works well in the digital data lifecycle to support the livestock sector and related animal health and welfare services (for endemic, exotic and foodborne disease preparedness and response)?
- What are the major challenges (gaps and roadblocks) now, and in the next 10 years, for the digitalisation of the livestock sector and related animal health and welfare services?

Our secondary aim was also to investigate attitudes, assumptions and risk perceptions amongst stakeholders, about:

- Current use of digital data in animal health management, for different farm systems.
- Technical, cultural, social or economic enablers or constraints related to acquisition, aggregation, management, application, use and benefits of digital data for livestock health and welfare.
- Other factors affecting digital adoption on farms, markets, abattoirs etc.
- Ethical, legal and regulatory issues which influence public and stakeholder opinion, trust and return value of digital data- including privacy protection and data sharing policies.
- Opportunities to strengthen digitalisation of the livestock sector to improve surveillance and livestock health and welfare (particularly for foodborne, endemic and exotic notifiable disease exemplars such as *Salmonella* infections, AMR and African swine fever).

Appendix 1. describes the implementation framework for the UK workshop (executed online and facilitated through a Miro board).

The Danish workshop was designed to mimic the structure of the UK workshop and re-use much of the prepared material and discussion topics, with some minor changes to suit the physical meeting format as well as to reflect the smaller and more inter-connected community of stakeholders in Denmark. Stakeholders were identified primarily through existing contacts of the Danish team, but also through snowballing through larger teams of relevant stakeholder organisations to identify further individuals. This resulted in invitations being accepted from a diverse spectrum of individuals, with a good balance between technical skills and policy oversight, as well as a roughly even distribution of primary interests distributed over our 3 case studies.

The first workshop in Sweden ² focused on data on antimicrobial use (AMU) and was carried out through the following steps:

- Identifying stakeholders throughout the data lifecycle and their role in the different parts of the life cycle
- Identifying the purpose to use AMU-data per stakeholder (keeping the data life cycle in mind)
- Brainstorming of possible visualization tools to increase return value to the stakeholders and improved basis for decision making, and more specifically to fulfil the identified purposes.
- Societal, technological, environmental, economic, and political (STEEP) challenges and opportunities to strengthen digitalisation and to enable the building of the tool. The

² A second workshop is planned next year to address African swine fever (ASF). The implementation design is not yet finalised.

identified challenges and opportunities were later also mapped in relation to the data life cycle.

Appendix I. Implementation Framework for the DigiVet Workshop (Miro Board)

What is the DigiVet project?

The DigiVet project will study how livestock data is currently used across the partner nations, and how technology, training, and regulatory frameworks might provide societal benefit by improving the public-interest uses of these data.

Successful management of livestock disease ensures a consistent supply of safe food for everyone in society. The use of data by industry, public services, and even the public at large is a key part of this veterinary public health mission.

For more info on the project, visit the [Project Overview](#)

What is our focus for today?

We would like your help with exploring the challenges in data digitalisation of the livestock sector and in identifying key opportunities for developing solutions.

Think about:

- Constraints** related to data acquisition, aggregation, management, use or benefits of digital data records for livestock health and welfare.
- Other key factors affecting **digital adoption** on farms, markets, abattoirs or other relevant sites.
- Ethical, legal and **regulatory issues** which may affect public or stakeholder opinion, trust and return value of digital data - including privacy protection and data sharing policies.
- Opportunities to strengthen digitalisation** of the livestock sector to improve surveillance and livestock health and welfare.

Return Value
Costs, Resource, User-Transparency, Skills, Expertise & Capacity, Risk & Benefits, Trust, Transparency etc.

Data Acquisition
Connectivity, Wearables, Remote sensing, Electronic Identification Data, Registers, Biobanks, Decision Support Tools, Diagnostics etc.

Data Aggregation & Processing
Unstructured Data Handling, Interoperability, Harmonisation with core standards etc.

Data Management & Maintenance
Data Formatting, Access, Security, Quality Assurance, Preservation etc.

Data Usage
Data Retrieval, Analytics & Insights for Policy Development & Decision-making, Harmonising Data Flow, Ethical etc.

Adapted from Shang, J., Srinivas, S., Agarwal, R., Yu, J., Patten, C., Aksoy, S. et al. (2012) Data lifecycle for the livestock data. In: Proc. 11th International Conference on Data Science and Information Systems. Springer, pp. 100-110.

Overview of today's workshop

What is working well?

What are the challenges?

What are the root causes?

If you had a magic wand?

We'll be working in small groups and meeting regularly to share our work and discuss

What currently works well in the digital data lifecycle to support the livestock sector and related animal health and welfare services?

Consider the following applications:

- Endemic disease control (e.g. salmonella, AMR)
- Exotic disease preparedness and response (e.g. African Swine Fever)

Electronic identifiers of livestock

Adapted from Zhang, J, Symons, J, Aggona, P, Teo, JF, Patton, CA, Abdi, L et al. (2022) Best practices in the real-world data life cycle. *PLoS Digit Health* 1(1): e0000003. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pdig.0000003>

What are the major challenges now, and in the next 10 years, for the digitalisation of the livestock sector and related animal health and welfare services?

Consider the following applications:

- Endemic disease control (e.g. salmonella, AMR)
- Exotic disease preparedness and response (e.g. African Swine Fever)

Which are the most critical challenges?

**What is the root cause
of the most critical
challenges?**

**If you had a magic
wand, how would you
solve these challenges?**